

EBFMC25-OP-77 · Evaluation of Applications to the University of Health Sciences Tepecik Training and Research Hospital Maternity School Following the Legislative Amendment

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Maternal, neonatal, and infant mortality rates are among the most important indicators of a successful healthcare system. In this context, educational programs targeting pregnant women and their families can lead to significant improvements. Informing families about pregnancy preparation, the gestational process, childbirth, and the postpartum period plays a crucial role in public health. Effective education provided by healthcare professionals helps pregnant women better recognize potential complications. These trainings raise awareness on topics such as the pregnancy process, normal vaginal delivery (NVD) and breastfeeding (Tuna, Karataş, Bilge, & Çelik, 2021). To serve this purpose, maternity schools have been established across the country. With the legislative amendment in December 2024, the promotion of vaginal birth and the strengthening of maternity schools were prioritized (Uğuz & Karaçam, 2022). In this regard, data from the maternity school in our hospital were evaluated.

Materials and Methods: Between January and March, 58 pregnant women enrolled in the program. The average age was 28.2, with 57.9% under the age of 30. Of the participants, 46.43% were in their first pregnancy, while 28.57% were in their second. Based on previous birth mode, 51.85% had a cesarean section, 25.93% had a NVD, and 22.22% had a history of abortion. Among those who gave birth during follow-up, 59.3% delivered via cesarean section, and 40.6% had a normal vaginal delivery. The training consisted of three sessions; 49.12% of participants attended all three. At the time of registration, 84.5% were in the third trimester, and 12.1% in the second. Partner participation was recorded at 12.07%.

Results: Data analysis revealed that nearly half of the participants attended all training sessions. The high participation rate among third-trimester women suggests that education is more frequently sought in later stages of pregnancy. This may indicate increased awareness due to repeated antenatal visits (Tuna et al., 2021).

Conclusion: The Prenatal Education Program has shown valuable contributions in informing and preparing pregnant women for childbirth, as reflected by the high attendance and continuity across all three sessions. The distribution of participants by age and gestational week indicates that the training successfully reaches a diverse population. However, the low rate of partner involvement points to the need for strengthening family-centered support structures. Starting maternity school programs earlier in pregnancy may lead to more effective knowledge and behavioral changes (Uğuz & Karaçam, 2022).

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Maternity school, prenatal education, maternal health

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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